

Eating Your Own Dogfood - A Project-Based Learning Experiment on an Open edX platform

Thomas Staubitz¹[0000-0002-8595-7922], Stefania Trabucchi²[0009-0005-0793-2198], and Eden Huthmacher³[0009-0002-6304-031X]

¹ German University of Digital Science, 14482 Potsdam, Germany
thomas.staubitz@german-uds.de

<https://german-uds.de>

² Abstract-Technology GmbH, 12101 Berlin, Germany
stefania.trabucchi@abstract-technology.de
<https://abstract-technology.de>

³ Axim Collaborative, Cambridge, MA 02142, USA
ehuthmacher@axim.org <https://axim.org>

Abstract. The German University of Digital Science is a new online-only university catering to a world-wide audience. *Coding Camp 1: Python* was one of a first set of micro-degree programs offered in October 2024. It covered basic Python, Django, open-source development, version control, and agile project management. After introducing the basics, the program followed a project-based learning (PBL) approach. The learners had to choose between designing and developing an application of their own from scratch or contributing to the Open edX open-source project. Experts from two of Open edX' main stakeholders supported the learners to accommodate for the steeper learning curve. The paper at hand discusses the intentions, goals and views of the learners and the other involved stakeholders.

Keywords: Project-based Learning · Collaborative Learning · Online Learning

1 Introduction

The German University of Digital Science⁴ is a new online-only university aiming to offer German university degrees to a world-wide audience. Students do not have to come to Germany to complete their study program, but can learn from wherever they are. This removes barriers to earning a European university degree—no visa, travel expenses, or high living costs. Graduates receive a state-approved German degree, enhancing their European job prospects. Before its official approval in Brandenburg⁵ (March 2025), German UDS beta-tested some of the study modules as micro-degree programs with real teachers and

⁴ <https://german-uds.de>

⁵ The German education system is a federal system. All universities are state-approved by the ministry of education of the federal state in which they are located.

learners. With the start of the study programs in April 2025, life-long-learners in the micro-degree programs are learning alongside the regular students in the Masters and MBA programs.

The paper at hand examines a project-based learning approach in one of these micro-degree programs⁶ offered in October 2024. This program’s main focus was on Python/Django programming, but it also covered basics of related topics, such as agile project management, refactoring, clean code, version control, SQL, open-source development, and open-source licenses. The program’s duration of 12 weeks, includes two preparation weeks, eight lecture weeks and two reflection weeks. The project work was conducted with two industry partners: Axim Collaborative, an NGO maintaining the Open edX project and Abstract-Technology, one of the main contributors to the project and the German UDS’ development service partner, responsible for setup, customisation, and hosting of the system.

2 Related Work

Project-based learning has been widely used in various learning contexts for its educational advantages[8]. Back in the 1930’s, Vygotsky delineated the *Zone of Proximal Development* [10]; a model claiming that students are capable of learning substantially better when they are not working isolated but can refer to some sort of guidance. This guidance can be provided either by the teachers themselves, by the learners’ peers, or by a scaffold setup by the teachers. Later Mitra showed that the guidance provided by peers actually is very effective in his work on the SOLE project where a group of learners had to share one computer and was forced to learn collaboratively [6]. Condliffe, et al [1], warn that the implementation of PBL can be challenging and requires a shift from a teacher-to a student-directed perspective and new forms of assessment. They encourage to add collaborative learning as one option to address the challenges [1]. Farrow, et al [3], delineate *the project* as the vehicle to promote the student-centeredness altering the students’ experience of learning [1]. The past two decades have witnessed a shift towards online learning. Examples are informal offers, such as the Khan Academy⁷ or MOOCs; or the more formal offers that emerged from those MOOCs, such as Georgia Tech’s online Computer Science Master⁸, MIT’s online Supply Chain Management Micro-masters⁹, or the German UDS’ fully online Masters’ and MBA programs¹⁰. The Covid pandemic or the war in Ukraine, showed an increasing demand for this shift, although many teachers and organisations did not embrace this opportunity and switched back to their old ways as soon as possible. Archambault, et al [4], point out that successful

⁶ https://apps.lms.german-uds.academy/learning/course/course-v1:LMS+CODE_python-1+2024_OCT

⁷ <https://www.khanacademy.org/>

⁸ <https://omscs.gatech.edu/>

⁹ <https://executive-ed.xpro.mit.edu/supply-chain-management>

¹⁰ <https://german-uds.de/study>

online education needs to focus on building relationships among the learners and incorporating active learning. Staubitz, et al [9], have examined team-based collaborative learning and PBL in MOOCs and showed a significant improvement of the learning quality for the small subset of learners that embraces this form of learning, while the majority of learners, who enjoy MOOCs as a form of edutainment, are not willing or not able to put in this amount of extra effort. Chujfi, et al [2], have successfully integrated the team processes into the assessment of team tasks and PBL. Building on these results and experiences, we have integrated a team-based PBL assignment in an online micro-degree program offered on the German UDS platform in October 2024.

3 Methodology

3.1 The micro-degree program

The micro-degree program consists of the phases listed in Table 1. Starting in Week4, the learners were guided through the process in weekly update meetings with the teacher—a one hour meeting per team and week. The program was

Table 1. Structure of the micro-degree program.

Phase	Description
Preparation	The learners were asked to participate in two of the Prep courses, which are offered on the German UDS open course platform free of charge for everybody. The two Prep courses were on the topics of Internet Basics ¹¹ and Web Basics ¹² .
Week1	Python basics. Variables, control structures, functions, etc.
Week2	Object Oriented Programming in Python
Week3	Django as a Python web development framework, minimal HTML, SQL, Django template language.
Week4	Version control, intro to agile development frameworks, such as Kanban or Scrum, etc.
The weeks' contents consisted of lecture videos, multiple choice tests and exams, several hands-on coding exercises, and a short warm-up project.	
Week5 - Week8	Project work in teams, office hours, presentations.
Reflection	At the end of the micro-degree program the learners had two more weeks to wrap things up and reflect on their learning.

offered in this constellation for the first time but the teacher of this course has a long history in offering MOOCs. Since 2013, he has created more than 30 courses with up to 20.000 participants. The numbers in this micro-degree program were much lower, 16 learners joined the course, 13 more or less actively followed the materials in Week1 to Week4. Seven learners actively participated in the project tasks, five of them successfully completed the course. The regular pricing of the micro-degree program is €900 but all of the enrolled learners joined the program

for free, using an “earlybird” voucher that was offered to attract a larger number of learners and also to give ourselves more freedom to experiment. Due to the free nature of the course and the lack of other implications caused by a dropout, the setting is, despite the numbers, more comparable to a MOOC than to a regular study program. A commonly used formula to calculate the completion rate for a MOOC [7, 5] is

$$\text{completion rate} = \frac{\text{issued certificates}}{\text{enrolled participants} - \text{no-shows}}$$

Following this approach, and considering the “enrollees” who didn’t start to be “no-shows”, the completion rate of this program would be around 38%¹³.

3.2 The project task

The guiding principles for the project tasks were:

1. it has to be a Python/Django project,
2. it should be meaningful to the learners or the learners environment,
3. and ideally a partner—industry partner or customer—is involved.
4. The contribution to an established open-source project was a plus.

Based on that, the micro-degree program offered two different tasks in the project phase as shown in Table 2. The focus of the rest of the paper at hand

Table 2. Offered project tasks and teams.

Team	Task
Team Green	Develop a Django application from scratch. The learners were asked to think about an application that would benefit their own life or the needs of an (ideally) real or imaginary customer. Create a project plan and implement an MVP. Features had to be prioritised, the team work had to be organised in an agile way and the code had to be under version control to allow collaboration and sharing.
Team Maintenance	Take over an open maintenance issue in the Open edX project. Open edX is an established open-source project, it serves as the basis for the German UDS’ learning platform, it is Python/Django based, improving the platform has a direct impact on the learners’ experience, and key players in the community—Axim Collaborative and Abstract-Technology—offered their support.

will be on the two learners who chose to work in Team Maintenance. At this point we will leave the three learners who chose to work in Team Green, even if their learning journey and approach really was impressive as well.

¹³ For a MOOC this is a quite respectable number.

3.3 The evaluation

Due to the small number of participants, we focused on a qualitative evaluation approach. The learners discussed their experience with the teacher and they were invited to discuss their experience in dedicated interviews with the industry partners. The survey results in the modules have no statistical significance but they support the more detailed qualitative data. The low sample size limits the generalisability of the results.

3.4 German UDS' perspective

The German UDS is offering practice-oriented study programs that include hands-on experience, ideally in direct cooperation with industry partners. Learners gain practical insights into real-world technologies and connect with potential employers for student jobs or early career opportunities. Involving organisations such as Axim Collaborative and Abstract-Technology in teaching fosters our community integration and strengthens relationships beyond business. We, therefore, consider the project a success from both organisational and instructional perspectives. While learners faced challenges, our grading approach ensured a safe environment without penalising failure—crucial in an unpredictable setting with many variables. To achieve this, the grading for this project consisted of three components:

1. Intermediate presentations during the weekly meetings between team and teacher (office hours). Informal progress updates to keep learners on track and prevent last-minute procrastination.
2. A final presentation allowed learners to share their journey. Each team member contributed, providing the teacher with evidence of their understanding.
3. A lab report documented both team and individual processes, providing a safe space for learners to fail without impacting their grades. The use of AI tools to polish their work was encouraged when documented. The report's format, incorporating personal experiences, resists simplistic AI-generated responses, while AI-assisted optimisation improved readability.

3.5 Learners' perspective

The program's active learners came from diverse backgrounds (70% male, 30% female), with 50% having a migration background or studying abroad. Aged 30–70, most were employees of large companies, with one retiree. All held graduate degrees, with motivations split between learning Python and a general interest in teamwork¹⁴. Out of the 16 enrolled learners¹⁵, 13 accessed at least one of the assignments in Week1 to Week4. Nine of them also submitted hands-on programming exercises, seven participated in the warm-up project, six in the

¹⁴ The numbers were collected in the program surveys

¹⁵ This is the net number of enrolled learners and already excludes all testers, teachers, and other non-learning stakeholders

final project that is the topic of the paper at hand. Of these six, two learners chose to work on the Open edX maintenance task. The other four, who chose to work on a self-designed application could be considered as a control group. However, the paper’s focus, particularly considering the small sample size, is not differentiating between projects that involve industry partners and those who do not.

3.6 Industry partners’ perspectives

The involved industry partners, Axim Collaborative and Abstract Technologies, have many common interests in joining this project, but there are also some subtle differences based on their respective roles in Open edX.

Axim Collaborative, as the NGO being responsible for the maintenance and sustainable development of the Open edX core platform, is always looking for ways to bring new contributors into the Open edX community and help them to succeed. One of the biggest challenges in open-source projects is attracting and retaining new contributors. Many developers hesitate to contribute due to the complexity of large-scale codebases, unclear entry points, or lack of guidance. Bringing students into the Open edX ecosystem benefits the entire community. More contributors mean more innovation, fresh perspectives, and ultimately a stronger, more sustainable platform. If even a small percentage of participants continue contributing beyond the course, that is a win for the Open edX project.

Abstract-Technology, as a company dedicated to delivering open-source Learning Management Systems (LMS) for educational institutions, carefully selects, designs, and customises innovative learning solutions for their clients. They proudly serve as a verified service partner of the Open edX LMS, which fits with their philosophy that is deeply rooted in the core principles of open-source: transparency, collaboration, and community. Abstract-Technology has actively supported initiatives that foster strong communities and the open exchange of knowledge in software development.

When the German UDS approached them with the idea of integrating real-world open-source contributions into their micro-degree program, it was an easy decision for both to support this initiative. For Axim Collaborative, the opportunity to introduce learners to Open edX’s tech stack, while also fostering a deeper understanding of open-source collaboration, aligned perfectly with their goals as stewards of the project. By partnering with German UDS, they saw an opportunity to create a structured, guided introduction to Open edX development. This allowed them to engage with motivated learners, who might not have otherwise considered contributing to an open-source project. Abstract, as the technology provider for the German UDS, saw this initiative as a highly valuable opportunity that they could envision evolving into a long-term collaboration, benefiting the university as well as its students and last not least the company in their effort to hire new talent. The goals of the industry partners aligned well with the course goals and extended them with some aspects. We all hoped that the participants would, successfully onboard onto the Open edX tech stack using Axim’s

dedicated developer onboarding course on the Open edX training site¹⁶, gain hands-on experience with open-source workflows, including version upgrades, repository tracking, technical feasibility testing, and other collaboration activities and become engaged members of the Open edX community. Both partners' engagement began with in-depths interviews conducted by the course instructor, which were delivered in Week4 of the micro-degree program. The interview with Abstract Technology provided a comprehensive overview of how a software development company operates. It explored methodologies, processes, tools, and the complexities of guiding open-source software along a commercial path. Additionally, it addressed key challenges such as why software projects can fail, offering a candid, insider perspective. The interview with Axim addressed similar topics but focused on the role of the gatekeeper and responsible maintainer of a large open source software project. Beyond knowledge-sharing, Abstract Technology's direct involvement extended to hands-on mentorship with the students facing challenges in setting up Open edX. Through a close, interactive approach, their developers worked side by side with the students, systematically analysing the setup process and troubleshooting technical roadblocks. This support took two distinct forms: first, a structured, step-by-step guidance model, where students were assisted in real-time whenever they encountered compilation errors or needed help interpreting tracking logs to debug and complete the installation. Second, a deeper analysis aimed at identifying not just individual mistakes but also broader open-source challenges that could impact future users. Axim provided the students with access to the Open edX project's communication channels and documentation.

4 Results

As mentioned in 3.1, the completion rate of the micro-degree program was around 38%. Looking at the participation patterns in graded assignments and exercises, the dropout reason can be clearly related to the project-based approach of the program and aligns with previous results [9]. This, however, also clearly indicates that completion rates cannot be the only metric of success. The two learners who initially participated in the projects and did not successfully complete the course, dropped out due to a lack of time caused by events unrelated to the course context. The learners who selected to work in Team Green, all listed a lack of experience and confidence in their skills as the main reason why they did not want to get involved into a large existing real world project. The learners in Team Maintenance struggled with project onboarding despite prior experience, facing steep entry barriers in setting up a local Open edX development environment. Only with late-stage support from one of Abstract's DevOps engineers were they unblocked, leaving insufficient time for the actual task. Since DevOps skills were not a core learning objective of the course, future iterations should include an early support session to prevent frustration. From this experience, Axim and Abstract identified a few key areas for improvement for their onboarding process:

¹⁶ <https://training.openedx.io/>

1. **Improved documentation:** The students' feedback identified gaps in documentation that require improvement. A key priority is the need for clearer, more structured, and version-specific documentation that ensures all installation steps are thoroughly explained. Task-specific guides should be developed to address common use cases, while separate documentation for Linux and macOS would help avoid confusion. Differing setup experiences based on operating systems were recognised. Open-source solutions often align more seamlessly with open-source OS than proprietary ones. Additionally, clearer statements on version requirements and compatibility would streamline the onboarding process for new users.
2. **Simplifying the installation process:** Particularly for Tutor on both macOS and Linux—remains an important goal. Regular maintenance reviews are essential to keep documentation up to date and to prevent outdated information from adding unnecessary complexity. Strengthening community support by offering expert-led sessions, improving response times to user queries, and developing a pre-configured environment for easier installation would further enhance accessibility. Moreover, introducing video tutorials or step-by-step screen recordings, despite the higher maintenance workload, could significantly improve the learning curve for newcomers.
3. **More structured onboarding support:** The setup process for the Open edX platform is complex, and we underestimated the level of assistance students would need. In future iterations, we would provide:
 - A dedicated onboarding session at the start of the project
 - Step-by-step setup guides¹⁷ tailored to first-time contributors.
 - Guidance on how to locate reliable resources for troubleshooting, roadmap insights, bug resolutions, and expert support.
 - Identification of recurring technical issues that may not be isolated cases but rather systemic challenges that should be addressed at the project level for global improvements.
 - Office hours or a dedicated chat channel¹⁸ (Slack or discourse) for troubleshooting
4. **Smaller, well-defined tasks:** Instead of assigning open maintenance issues, which can vary widely in complexity, we plan to curate a list of beginner-friendly tasks. These will focus on incremental improvements that learners can realistically complete within the course timeframe.
5. **Mentorship and peer support:** Encouraging learners to work in small teams and pairing them with experienced Open edX contributors could help ease the onboarding process. Having a mentor or peer to check in with regularly might prevent frustration from becoming a blocker.
6. **Encouraging long-term involvement:** While this was a short-term project, we would love to see some of these learners continue contributing to the Open edX Project. We will explore ways to keep them engaged, such as inviting them to Open edX community meetings, hackathons, or future contribution sprints.

¹⁷ <https://docs.openedx.org/en/latest/>

¹⁸ <https://openedx.org/community/connect/>

The results of the course end survey show that despite the obstacles, the learners in Team Maintenance were highly satisfied with the program. Both of them completed the survey. The answer options were on a 5-point Likert-scale. The course covered the expected topics (4.6), the materials were engaging (4.6), the content was up-to-date (5.0), I want to pursue further learning or projects in Python (5.0), the team-based project helped me to learn the dynamics of software development (4.5), I feel confident writing Python code(4.5), the course helped me understand the software development process (4.5), the technical aspects of the course worked smoothly (5.0), pace and duration of the contents were appropriate for my learning (4.0), I felt actively engaged and motivated throughout the course (5.0), The examples used in the course were relevant and helpful (5.0), the teacher explained the concepts clearly (5.0). In comparison, only one of four members of Team Green completed the survey with a similar at times a tad lower results. Again, due to the small number of responses, these results cannot be generalised in any way.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This hands-on collaboration not only empowered the students but also provided invaluable feedback to the broader Open edX community, reinforcing the iterative and community-driven nature of open-source development. We saw strong engagement from those who persisted. The participants demonstrated enthusiasm and dedication, producing detailed lab reports that reflected a deep learning experience. All three partners are looking forward to continuing their partnership and repeating this offer for the learners in the future. The experiment has revealed where Open edX' onboarding material needs to be improved to flatten the steep learning curve. Despite the initial challenges, this collaboration was an invaluable experiment in integrating open-source contribution into formal education. In conclusion it was a win-win situation for all stakeholders: The students who completed the project walked away with real-world coding experience, Axim and the Open edX community gained fresh contributors and valuable feedback on improving its accessibility to newcomers, the German UDS was able to provide a useful task for the student project and the industry support strongly unburdened the workload from the teacher. Both Axim Collaborative and Abstract-Technology gained valuable insights how to improve processes and documentation. With some refinements to the onboarding process and project selection, we are confident that future iterations will be even more impactful. Projects connecting learners/students to real life problems, strongly contribute to a meaningful, competency-based education even if the main focus of the program's learning objectives are slightly missed. The experience they gained in setting up a development version of an open-source project, the insights into the workflows and decision processes of an open-source project, and the direct connection to their own learning environment, a system that they work with everyday for the time of their studies, outweighs the obstacles, pitfalls, and finally the lack of time to work on their actual task. As emphasised by the European

EdTech Alliance, a robust framework where academia, research institutions, and commercial providers collaborate is essential. By working together to test, evaluate, and refine software solutions beyond institutional barriers and competing interests, we can prioritise education as a universally accessible resource. Ultimately, the success of projects like Open edX depends on the shared commitment to making high-quality learning tools available to everyone, everywhere.

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